

Association of body mass index in adolescence and young adulthood and long-term risk of Multiple Sclerosis: A population-based study
eTables

Category	BMI category	Cases	Non-cases	Adjusted ¹ HR, 95% CI
All	Underweight	107	64,734	0.82 (0.67-1.00)
	Normal	957	483,967	Ref
	Overweight	142	64,416	1.14 (0.96-1.36)
	Obese	99	32,105	1.60 (1.30-1.97)
Males	Underweight	36	31,083	0.93 (0.66-1.32)
	Normal	284	232,423	Ref
	Overweight	55	30,987	1.48 (1.11-1.97)
	Obese	28	15,412	1.52 (1.03-2.24)
Females	Underweight	71	33,651	0.77 (0.60-0.98)
	Normal	673	251,544	Ref
	Overweight	87	33,429	1.00 (0.80-1.25)
	Obese	71	16,693	1.64 (1.28-2.09)
Age 14-19 yrs	Underweight	51	22,440	0.75 (0.56-1.00)
	Normal	503	167,586	Ref
	Overweight	75	22,288	1.12 (0.88-1.43)
	Obese	56	11,113	1.68 (1.28-2.22)
Age 20-34 yrs	Underweight	56	42,294	0.88 (0.67-1.16)
	Normal	454	316,381	Ref
	Overweight	67	42,128	1.16 (0.90-1.50)
	Obese	43	20,992	1.50 (1.10-2.05)

eTable 1: Multiple sclerosis risk according to body mass index (BMI) at tuberculosis screening, age and sex-specific percentiles: <10% =underweight, ≥10% to 84% =normal weight, ≥85 to 94% = overweight, ≥95%=obese. Analysis excluding first 5 years of follow up after BMI screening. ¹Adjusted for age at screening, sex, birth year and county. HR – Hazard ratio

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Category	BMI category	Cases	Non-cases	Ajusted ¹ HR, 95% CI
All	Underweight	30	11,310	0.92 (0.63-1.35)
	Normal	214	75,253	Ref
	Overweight	23	9,110	0.90 (0.58-1.38)
	Obese	25	4,479	1.97 (1.30-2.99)
Males	Underweight	5	5,506	0.49 (0.20-1.21)
	Normal	67	35,718	Ref
	Overweight	9	4,402	1.09 (0.54-2.19)
	Obese	8	2,221	1.88 (0.90-3.92)
Females	Underweight	25	5,804	1.12 (0.73-1.71)
	Normal	147	39,535	Ref
	Overweight	14	4,708	0.81 (0.47-1.41)
	Obese	17	2,258	2.03 (1.23-3.35)
Age 14-19 yrs	Underweight	13	3,186	0.54 (0.34-0.87)
	Normal	86	23,644	Ref
	Overweight	11	3,024	1.09 (0.78-1.54)
	Obese	9	1,489	1.73 (1.19-2.53)
Age 20-34 yrs	Underweight	17	8,124	0.82 (0.50-1.1.37)
	Normal	128	51,609	Ref
	Overweight	12	6,086	0.81 (0.45-1.46)
	Obese	16	2,990	2.13 (1.27-3.58)

eTable 2: Multiple sclerosis risk according to body mass index (BMI) at tuberculosis screening, with age and sex-specific percentiles: <10% =underweight, ≥10% to 84% =normal weight, ≥85 to 94% = overweight, ≥95%=obese. Analysis restricted to Hordaland and Telemark County. ¹Adjusted for age at screening, sex, birth year and county. HR – Hazard ratio

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Category	BMI category	Cases	Non-cases	Ajusted ¹ HR, 95% CI
All	Underweight	21	22,501	1.00 (0.63-1.57)
	Normal	161	167,958	Ref
	Overweight	17	22,353	0.79 (0.48-1.30)
	Obese	20	11,133	1.89 (1.19-3.01)
Males	Underweight	8	11,499	0.78 (0.38-1.62)
	Normal	80	86,066	Ref
	Overweight	4	11,449	0.37 (0.13-1.01)
	Obese	11	5,705	2.10 (1.12-3.95)
Females	Underweight	13	11,002	1.20 (0.67-2.16)
	Normal	81	81,892	Ref
	Overweight	13	10,904	1.22 (0.68-2.20)
	Obese	9	5,428	1.71 (0.86-3.40)

eTable 3: Multiple sclerosis risk according to body mass index (BMI) at tuberculosis screening, with age and sex-specific percentiles: <10% =underweight, ≥10% to 84% =normal weight, ≥85 to 94% = overweight, ≥95%=obese. Cases ascertained through the Norwegian Cause of Death Registry. Cases also found in the Norwegian MS registry and biobank excluded. Restricted to participants aged 14 to 19 years at screening. ¹Adjusted for age at screening, sex, birth year and county. HR – Hazard ratio